

KOSTANECKI-ROBINSON REACTION. PART V. BENZOYLATION OF SOME *o*-HYDROXY KETONES

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3-Benzoylflavone derivatives have been isolated in the Kostanecki-Robinson benzylation of resacetophenone, 2-acetylresorcinol and phloracetophenone by using the experimental technique developed by Sethna and Shah.

In a previous paper Sethna and Shah (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 601) benzoylated oracetophenone and in the course of this work, developed a new technique of working up the benzoylated product which enabled them to isolate the 3-benzoylflavone derivative formed.

Their experimental technique consists in treating the reaction mixture after benzylation with petroleum ether and water to remove benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate respectively which makes possible the isolation of flavones with both the *O*- and the *C*-benzoyl groups intact. The *O*-benzoyl group can then be removed smoothly by the use of concentrated sulphuric acid, leaving the 3-benzoyl group intact. This new technique has now been employed for the isolation of 3-benzoylflavones in the case of benzylation of other *o* hydroxy-ketones. A slight modification introduced by the present authors is the use of carbon disulphide in the place of petroleum ether.

Resacetophenone 2-acetylresorcinol and phloracetophenone have been benzoylated and the reaction mixture treated with carbon disulphide and water to remove benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate respectively and 7-benzoyloxy-3-benzoylflavone, 5-benzoyloxy-3-benzoylflavone and 5:7-dibenzoyloxy-3-benzoylflavone have been isolated. These on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid give 7-hydroxy 3-benzoylflavone, 5-hydroxy-3-benzoylflavone and 5:7-dihydroxy-3-benzoylflavone respectively. The 3-benzoylflavones may be debenzoylated by treatment with alcoholic potash. The method of Sethna and Shah has, therefore, been found to be of general applicability in the isolation of 3-benzoylflavones in the Kostanecki-Robinson benzylation of *o*-hydroxy-ketones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzylation of Resacetophenone: 7-Benzoyloxy-3-benzoylflavone.—An intimate mixture of resacetophenone (2 g.), sodium benzoate (6 g.) and benzoic anhydride (20 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 180-190° for 10 hours. The reaction product was extracted with about 100 c.c. of carbon disulphide to remove benzoic anhydride and the residue thoroughly washed with water to remove sodium benzoate. It was finally treated with sodium bicarbonate and then with water. The crude product crystallised from alcohol-acetone mixture (1:1) in long needles (1 g.), m.p. 167°. Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1381) gives the same m.p. The product is insoluble in alkali.

7-Hydroxy-3-benzoylflavone.—The above dibenzoylflavone (0.8 g.) was kept in contact with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) overnight. The solution was poured into cold water and the product was crystallised from alcohol in prisms (0.4 g.), m.p. 264-65°. Rangaswamy and Seahdri (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 10A, 6) give m.p. 265°. It readily dissolves in cold dilute alkali giving a pale yellow solution.

7-Hydroxyflavone.—7-Hydroxy-3-benzoylflavone (1 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potash (10%, 15 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The excess of alcohol was distilled off and the solution

acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a product separated which was crystallised from alcohol in long colourless needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 240°. Rangaswami and Seshadri (*loc. cit.*) and Baker (*loc. cit.*) give the same m.p.

Benzoylation of 2-Acetylresorcinol: 5-Benzoyloxy-3-benzoylflavone.—An intimate mixture of 2-acetylresorcinol (2 g.), sodium benzoate (6 g.) and benzoic anhydride (20 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 180-90° for 9 hours. The fused mass was powdered, extracted with carbon disulphide, then thoroughly washed with water and the residue then washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water as in the previous case. The product was crystallised from acetone in yellow plates (0.9 g.), m.p. 234-35°. It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali. (Found : C, 79.9; H, 4.7. $C_{28}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 80.4; H, 4.3 per cent).

5-Hydroxy-3-benzoylflavone.—The above dibenzoylflavone (1 g.) was kept in contact with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) overnight. The product obtained on pouring this into cold water was crystallised from ethyl acetate in yellow prisms (0.7 g.), m.p. 174-75°. Sugasawa (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1483) gives m.p. 174°.

5-Hydroxyflavone.—5-Hydroxy-3-benzoylflavone (1 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potash (10%, 15 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the product obtained on working up as before was crystallised from alcohol in thin yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 156-57°. Sugasawa (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 157°.

Benzoylation of Phloracetophenone: 5:7-Dibenzoyloxy-3-benzoylflavone.—An intimate mixture of phloracetophenone (2 g.), sodium benzoate (6 g.) and benzoic anhydride (20 g.) was heated in an oil-bath for 8 hours at 180-90°. The fused mass was extracted with carbon disulphide, the residue was thoroughly washed with water and then washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The crude product, thus obtained, was crystallised from alcohol-acetone mixture (1:1) in tiny white needles (1.3 g.), m.p. 167-68°. It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali. (Found : C, 76.0; H, 4.0. $C_{32}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 76.3; H, 4.1 per cent).

5:7-Dihydroxy-3-benzoylflavone.—The above flavone (0.8 g.) was kept in contact with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) overnight and the resulting product on pouring in cold water was crystallised from dilute alcohol (50%) in small prisms (0.5 g.), m.p. 145-46°. It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali giving a yellow solution. (Found : C, 73.4; H, 4.3. $C_{28}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 73.7; H, 3.9 per cent).

5:7-Dihydroxyflavone (Chrysin).—5:7-Dihydroxy-3-benzoylflavone (1 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potash (10%, 15 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the product obtained on working up the reaction mixture as before, was crystallised from alcohol in small prismatic needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 174-75°. Robinson and Venkataraman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2347) give m.p. 275°.